

SPORT AND GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE POLICY AND LEGISLATION: COUNTRY PROFILES

10 December 2025

In Collaboration With

About the Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport

[The Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport \(GO\)](#) monitors progress towards gender equality in sport+. The GO is a global convenor and repository of research and expertise on gender equality and sport, physical education, and physical activity – or sport+ for short. The GO is creating a knowledge pool on women & gender related issues and bringing together diverse actors in sport in order to tackle them. The GO is an international NGO based in Lausanne, Switzerland. Established in July 2021 with the support of UNESCO and the Swiss Confederation, the GO is an initiative originated from UNESCO's 4th International Conference of Ministers and Senior Officials Responsible for Physical Education and Sport (MINEPS IV) in Athens, Greece, in 2003. The commitment to the GO was reinforced by the 2017 Kazan Action Plan (KAP) at MINEPS VI, in Kazan, Russia and further reaffirmed at MINEPS VII in Baku, Azerbaijan, in 2023, with support from over 100 member states.

About Global Sport Policy Tracker

Developed and led by Emily Cameron-Blake, a sport policy specialist, and other experts from academia, non-governmental organisations, charities, and from international advocacy groups in physical education, physical activity and sport (PEPAS). The Global Sport Policy Tracker is both a live dataset of sport policies and frameworks, and a tool for researchers and practitioners. The Global Sport Policy Tracker was developed to fill a void in systematically collected sport policy data - allowing for proper comparison of policies and frameworks in sport, internationally.

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Introduction

The Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport (GO) aims to monitor progress towards gender equality, including progress in combatting gender-based violence, in sport. The GO undertakes tracking of state actions towards creating safe and inclusive sporting environments. In partnership with [Global Sport Policy Tracker](#), the GO undertook a study to map policy and legislative actions across 12 countries which encompasses: **Types of GBV related criminal offences; Age of minority and consent; Duty to report child abuse; Mandatory screening for sport workers; GBV and Sport Laws and Policies; and Treaties and Reservations.** This is part of the GO's initiative to monitor policy and legislative action to prevent and respond to gender-based violence in sport as an indicator of gender equality.

Prevalence and impact of **gender-based violence (GBV)**, *violence directed against a person because of that person's gender (including gender identity/expression) or violence that affects persons of a particular gender disproportionately*, has long been an issue at all levels of sport and physical education, but has increasingly come to the public attention as requiring urgent consideration. (See: [CEDAW](#), [Council of Europe](#), [Maputo Protocol](#), [UNESCO](#))

Forms of GBV in the sporting context include sexual, physical, psychological/emotional, verbal, economic, and forms of discrimination and grooming. How each country defines and deals with these forms of violence vary as greatly as the circumstances in which they may occur. The behaviours and forms of violence which are considered to be criminal offences in one country may differ drastically from another. Similarly, while almost

all countries have legislation on preventing and addressing forms of violence against children – the definition of a child and age at which an individual is no longer considered to be a child for certain forms of violence typically range from 11-18 years. Women may also be considered a particularly vulnerable or protected class of people, benefiting from an extended list of behaviours and forms of violence which are considered to be criminal offences.

However, despite these criminal legislations, and legally protected peoples, whether these forms of GBV experienced in the sport context or environment are contemplated under criminal law, or whether all sport participants are protected by some other policy or legislation remains to be determined. Extensive mapping of the policies and legislations that cover and protect all sport and physical education participants in each country is required to determine whether individuals are falling through the gaps and remain at particular risk of GBV in sport globally. Further, the levels of sport participation covered by specific codes and regulatory oversight vary and are not uniformly applicable across the spectrum of recreational to elite sport. These variations leave room for some groups to be unprotected from certain forms of violence/prohibited behaviour. The Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport in collaboration with [Global Sport Policy Tracker](#) therefore developed a study to map the national policies and legislation related to GBV and Sport.

Framework of the Policy and Legislative Mapping of GBV and Sport

To discern where sport participants may be at increased risk of GBV - and where they may also be lacking legal or regulatory protections from GBV - it is necessary to first systematically map the policy and legal landscape of forms of GBV in the sporting context, in each country. To do this, the following framework was developed and applied in this study:

- **International Conventions and Charters:** For any international conventions or charters that the country is a signatory - indicate whether they have made any comments/reservations to any part of the text
 - Does this include to a potential protected class of peoples (for example LGBTQ+ populations, etc).
- **Forms of Gender Based Violence:** For each form of GBV in sport (physical, sexual, psychological/emotional, verbal, economic, grooming, discrimination) determine whether a country's legal system includes or contemplates it, and whether it is deemed to be a criminal offence, or whether other existing policies contemplate these forms of behaviour as GBV.
 - Determine whether the form of GBV is contemplated for all people, or whether just for certain groups (i.e., women, children, disabled, etc)
 - Identify the groups who are not contemplated by legislation or policy
- **Context of Sport in Which Legislation is Applicable:** For each form of GBV, indicate whether the associated legislation contemplates the behaviour in a sporting context. If so, is it in one or all of the following:
 - Elite sport
 - Sport/physical activity
 - Physical education
 - E-sport (online sport environments)
- **Actions and Mechanisms Addressing GBV:** Determine whether there are any National action plans, policies or strategies on combatting GBV
 - Do they include sport at any level?
- **Legal Age of Consent:** Determine the legal age of children vs adults for each country
- **Screening Requirements:** Determine the minimum screening requirements for those who work in sport
 - With children
 - Vulnerable groups (and how are they defined in country?)
 - With all other sport participants (especially adults)
- **Public Registry of Sanctioned Persons:** Indicate whether there is a public registry of those who have been found to be sanctioned for offences in sport (at all levels, or just some levels?)

Dataset Publication and Free Access

The data collected through this study will be useable for both qualitative and quantitative data analysis processes, ensuring that the context and nuance of varying policies and legislations on GBV are incorporated.

This report presents the briefs per country, the full dataset and code book are available for free download on the [GO repository](#) and project Github page.

In this first report, data from 12 countries has been collected; Australia, Canada, France, India, Ireland, Mexico, Morocco, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sweden, Switzerland, Zambia

All data collected will be shared and disseminated in a FAIR manner: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Data will be collected and distributed through the Global Observatory Knowledge Hub and GitHub repository under a CC By license, in partnership with the Global Sport Policy Tracker. The country profiles and dataset are a useful resource for governments, researchers, advocacy groups, and media practitioners and others. The second phase of the project will extend the dataset with entries covering more countries. The Global Observatory invited collaborators to join the project and welcomes wide use and circulation of the data.

AUSTRALIA

Australia's Comprehensive Framework for Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Sport and Child Protection

Australia has established an extensive series of policies and frameworks addressing gender-based violence (GBV) that explicitly recognize sport environments as critical spaces requiring intervention and prevention strategies. This approach combines national plans, sport-specific integrity frameworks, and child protection principles to create comprehensive protections, particularly for women, girls, and children.

National GBV Plan and Definitions

The [National Plan to End Violence Against Women and Children 2022-2032](#) explicitly identifies sporting organizations as having a vital role to play in ending GBV. The plan lists sporting clubs as possible sites of sexual violence and harassment, while recognizing men and boys as sports players who must be part of the solution. Sport organizations are specifically identified as places where prevention approaches must be embedded. The [Outcomes Framework](#) sub-outcome 3.5 indicates that “gender equality, positive relationships, and positive masculinities are promoted across the community including in faith-based, sporting, entertainment, educational institutions, digital spaces, the arts, and media organisations”, highlighting sporting spaces are key to driving cultural change with regard to GBV.

Australia's definition of GBV aligns with the United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women, recognizing GBV as violence rooted in historically unequal power relations that view women and girls as subordinate to men and boys. The plan acknowledges that 95% of people who have experienced physical or sexual violence

identify a man as the perpetrator, and approximately 4 in 5 family and domestic violence offenders are men. Violence encompasses physical, sexual, emotional, psychological, social, cultural, spiritual, financial, and technology-facilitated abuse, occurring across all settings including sport environments.

Sport-Specific Frameworks

Australia combats abuse in sport, including forms of gender-based violence, through [Sport Integrity Australia's National Integrity Framework](#), which establishes comprehensive policies addressing discrimination, harassment, child abuse, and sexual misconduct across all sport levels and all types of participants, and the [Safeguarding in Sport Continuous Improvement Program](#) (SISCIP). The SISCIP is underpinned by the [Safeguarding Children and Young People Policy](#), and the [10 National Principles for Child Safe Organisations](#).

The SISCIP is designed to help sporting organisations to build their capability to provide safe environments for children, young people and all members to participate in sport. This includes protecting them from abuse, providing safe and inclusive experiences and highlighting that safeguarding is the responsibility of everyone involved in sport.

Sport Integrity Australia also provides independent reporting channels for abuse in sport including the Safe Sport hotline offering anonymous reporting capability year-round.

However, there are limitations to what forms of abuse or GBV can be reported directly to SIA. Forms of abuse and GBV that fall within the Safeguarding Children and Young People Policy can be directly reported to SIA, while forms of abuse and GBV that fall within the Member's Protection Policy

(with the exception of discrimination) are reported to the sport body in which the harm occurred, not directly to SIA. This difference in reporting channels means that adult victims of GBV may fall outside of the scope of SIA's remit and protection. As each sport may have varying degrees of protection offered by their Complaints Disputes and Discipline policy, consistency in addressing abuse and GBV of adult sport participants may vary.

The [National Sport Strategy 2024-2034](#) explicitly mentions gendered violence and other violence relating to children and all sport members under its safety priorities. The [Empowering Women and Girls in Sport Integrity Program](#) specifically tackles critical issues including abuse, bullying, harassment, sexual misconduct, discrimination, victimization, and vilification, aiming to identify integrity threats facing women and girls in sport. Victoria's state-level initiative, "[Safe and Inclusive Sport – Preventing Gender-Based Violence](#)," provides guidance applicable to all sport levels, and is an example of how states are tackling GBV in sport.

Announced in 2024, Australia's [National Gender Equity in Sports Governance Policy](#) mandates that by July 2027, 50% of board directors, chairs/deputy chairs, and specified sub-committee members must be women and/or gender diverse. The [Sport Governance Standards](#) require boards to demonstrate commitment to diversity, equity and inclusion by setting composition goals, ensuring no single gender exceeds 50%. This structural change in governance addresses power imbalances that may enable gender-based violence in sport.

Child Protection and Legal Framework

The [National Strategy to Prevent and Respond to Child Sexual Abuse 2021-2030](#) lists sporting organizations as having key roles in providing services to children in child-safe ways. The legal adult age is 18 in Australia, though sexual consent ages vary by state and territory: 16 years in New South Wales, Queensland, Victoria, Western Australia, Northern Territory, and Australian Capital Territory; 17 years in South Australia and Tasmania. Australia maintains mandatory reporting requirements at state and territorial levels for all forms of child abuse.

Higher Education and Emerging Issues

In 2024 Australia developed and proposed the [National Higher Education Code to Prevent and Respond to Gender-Based Violence](#), with accompanying legislation requiring institutional compliance with the code passing Parliament in August 2025. However, this code does not specifically mention sport. The [Online Safety Act 2021](#) addresses technology-facilitated violence, relevant to esports and gaming environments. Australia participates in the [Global Partnership for Action on Gender-Based Online Harassment and Abuse](#), recognizing interlinkages between technology-facilitated violence against children and technology-facilitated gender-based violence.

Indigenous Communities

The [Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Action Plan 2023-2025](#) aims to end gender-based violence in one generation, though it does not specifically mention sport, reflecting the need for culturally appropriate approaches, and potential further expansion.

CANADA

Canada's Integrated Approach to Gender-Based Violence Prevention in Sport & Child Protection

Canada has developed a multi-layered framework addressing gender-based violence (GBV) that explicitly recognizes sport environments as critical spaces requiring targeted intervention. This approach combines federal legislation, national action plans, provincial and territorial laws, and sport-specific policies to create comprehensive protections for vulnerable populations, particularly children and youth.

National Action Plan and Federal Strategy

The [National Action Plan to End Gender-Based Violence](#) represents Canada's commitment to addressing GBV across multiple sectors, explicitly including sport. The plan identifies sports coaches and recreational activity staff as professionals requiring training and guidance on trauma-informed approaches for preventing and addressing GBV in the communities they serve. This recognition acknowledges that sport environments can facilitate or prevent violence depending on the awareness and preparedness of those in authority positions.

The plan emphasizes that marginalized and vulnerable groups—including Indigenous women, Black and racialized women, non-binary and gender-diverse people, 2SLGBTQI+ individuals, those in Northern rural and remote communities, people with disabilities, migrants, and children and youth—experience disproportionately high rates of gender-based violence. Critically, intersecting identity factors compound a person's risk and vulnerability. The Action Plan mandates that prevention must occur across public spaces, community spaces, workplaces,

educational settings, and post-secondary institutions, which logically extends to sport, physical education, physical activity areas, and potentially esports environments.

Canada's broader strategy, ["It's Time: Canada's Strategy to Prevent and Address Gender-Based Violence,"](#) addresses gaps in supports for diverse populations, though it does not explicitly mention sport, physical education, or physical activity settings.

Legal Framework for Protection

Canada's [sexual consent laws](#), with a base age of 16 nationally and close-in-age exceptions (12-13 year olds with partners less than 2 years older; 14-15 year olds with partners less than 5 years older), provide fundamental protection against exploitation. These laws explicitly prohibit consent when power imbalances exist—when an older partner holds a position of trust or authority, when dependency exists, or when relationships are exploitative. This directly addresses dynamics prevalent in sport where coaches and authority figures may perpetrate abuse.

Federal criminal legislation addresses family violence and child protection comprehensively, including assault, sexual assault, sexual offenses against children and youth, child pornography, trafficking, and exploitation – all of which are relevant in sport settings. Each province and territory maintains its own complementary legislation and child protection laws, with varying ages of minority and specific [duty-to-report](#) requirements. While child protection is provincial jurisdiction, the federal government maintains criminal law authority over child abuse through the Criminal Code.

Sport-Specific Frameworks

The [Universal Code of Conduct to Prevent and Address Maltreatment in Sport](#) (UCCMS) has been developed for the Canadian sport sector, but adoption is voluntary. While it does not explicitly state "gender-based violence," it covers all forms of maltreatment that constitute GBV, including discrimination based on gender. The [Canadian Safe Sport Program](#) (CSSP) is mandatory for federally funded high-performance levels of sport and provides the rules for adopting and applying the UCCMS, reporting and investigation of violations of the UCCMS, and issues sanctions for violations of the UCCMS. The CSSP also operates a national [safe sport registry](#) of individuals who have been sanctioned for violations of the UCCMS/CSSP, and whose participation in sport has been limited.

[The Red Deer Declaration](#) of February 2019 established collaborative commitments for preventing harassment, abuse, and discrimination in sport across jurisdictions. The Canadian Sport Policy reinforces that all sport and physical activity environments must be safe for everyone—men, women, children, and officials—at all levels of participation.

Quebec's Distinct Approach

Notably, Quebec implements its own initiatives for tackling GBV rather than adopting national government programs, though it receives federal funding to do so. This reflects Canada's federalist structure, allowing provincial autonomy while maintaining consistent protection standards.

Emerging Considerations

The [National Strategy for the Protection of Children from Sexual Exploitation on the Internet](#) may relate to esports environments and online grooming of athletes through digital devices, representing an evolving area of GBV prevention that intersects with modern sport participation.

This comprehensive framework demonstrates Canada's recognition that addressing gender-based violence requires coordinated action across legal, policy, and sport-specific domains, with particular attention to the unique vulnerabilities present in athletic environments.

FRANCE

France's Approach to Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Sport

France has developed a comprehensive framework to begin addressing gender-based violence (GBV) in sport through national action programs, ministerial oversight, federation responsibilities, and international alignment. This multi-layered approach combines legislation, policy, prevention measures, victim support, and strengthened criminal responses to create safer sporting environments, particularly for women and girls.

National Legal and Policy Framework, Ministry Leadership

France's approach is anchored in [national GBV action programs](#) and laws that provide the legal and policy backdrop for sport-specific measures. In 2018, [new legislation](#) strengthened France's fight against gender-based violence, creating an enhanced framework within which abuse or GBV in sport might be considered.

Sport is regulated through legislation via the [Code du Sport](#) in France, with stipulations and mandates for how sport is governed. National governing bodies of sport are [required to ensure compliance with the Charter of Sports Ethics](#) published by the French National Olympic and Sports Committee. The [Charter of Sports Ethics](#), explicitly states that verbal, physical, sexual, and psychological violence, along with discrimination, will not be tolerated. All approved sports federations must comply with this charter and integrate safeguarding into their statutes, competitions, coach education, licensing, and internal complaints procedures.

In 2024, the Ministry of Sport launched a new abuse reporting mechanism, [Signal Sports](#), strengthening pathways for sport participants and victims to report incidents safely. This system links

sport organizations directly to police, social services, and victim support networks through multi-agency referral pathways.

Protections for children

Following a 2021 scandal involving over 400 adults in abuse or cover-up cases within sport, in March 2024 France [updated the French Sport Code](#) to include mandatory screening of employees and certain volunteer positions in sport, ensuring individuals do not have criminal histories or backgrounds that make them unfit to participate in sport. This screening requirement appears to apply specifically to those working with minors, representing a targeted child protection measure within the broader sport system.

In 2021 France implemented an [age of consent law](#) determining that sexual activity with a person under 15 years is criminal activity in France, with close-in-age exceptions where individuals up to 5 years older may engage in consensual activity with those aged 15 and above. France maintains a national [duty to report child abuse](#), obligating all citizens to report suspected cases.

Gender Equality and Prevention Initiatives

France has demonstrated strong commitment to gender equality through its Feminization Plans of Sports Federations, initiated in 2016. By March 2016, 86 sports federations had developed feminization plans promoting women's participation, leadership, and equality. These plans provide visibility into best practices across federations and enable partnerships supporting sport development for all genders.

French sport federations are also required to implement event-level safeguarding frameworks for major competitions, and awareness campaigns

addressing sexual harassment, abuse of power, and harmful gendered norms in sport. France aligns these measures with Council of Europe initiatives including "All In Plus" recommendations and the [High-Level Group on Gender Equality in Sport recommendations](#).

In 2023, France created the "[Terrain d'égalité](#)" (Equality Ground) label to recognize major international sporting events committed to promoting equality between women and men while preventing and combating discrimination and gender-based sexual violence. This initiative reflects France's preparation for hosting the 2024 Paris Olympics and established accountability standards for major sporting events.

Ongoing Challenges

Despite significant progress, persistent gaps remain including uneven implementation across smaller clubs and grassroots settings, variability in monitoring and enforcement, and continued under-reporting of abuse and GBV in sport. Additionally, France's ban on religious symbols such as the hijab in sporting competitions—including for French athletes at the 2024 Paris Olympics and across all levels of football, basketball, and volleyball—is considered by some to create [unsafe conditions](#) for women and girls from marginalized or minority cultural backgrounds, highlighting tensions between national policies and inclusive sport environments.

INDIA

India's Evolving Approach to Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Society and Sport

India has taken significant steps to address gender-based violence (GBV) in society and sport, though implementation remains inconsistent and challenged by systemic gaps. The country's approach combines general legal provisions, specialized workplace protections, domestic violence legislation, and newly enacted sport-specific laws to create frameworks for prevention and accountability.

National GBV Framework and Legal Protections

India's legal framework addressing GBV includes several key pieces of legislation. The [Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act](#) provides civil remedies for women experiencing domestic abuse, establishing protection orders and support mechanisms. The [Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace \(Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal\) Act of 2013](#) addresses workplace harassment, though its application to sport environments faces limitations. The [Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act \(POCSO\)](#) specifically criminalizes sexual offenses against minors, providing crucial protections for young athletes. The [Indian Penal Code \(IPC\)](#) contains provisions addressing physical assault and various forms of violence, though procedural challenges often hinder effective implementation.

Reporting Mechanisms and Implementation Challenges

The Indian government has established women's police stations, police desks, and [One-Stop Centres](#) throughout the country for reporting crimes and accessing support services. According to 2021 data, implementing women's police stations has increased domestic violence reporting rates,

demonstrating some success in creating accessible reporting pathways. Training programs on GBV exist for police, judiciary, and medical officers to improve response capabilities. However, policing remains inconsistent in GBV cases, with some officers taking no action, refusing to register cases, or encouraging reconciliation rather than pursuing justice. This inconsistency undermines victims' access to protection and accountability, particularly affecting athletes who face additional barriers in reporting abuse by coaches or officials in positions of authority.

Sport-Specific Challenges Before 2025

Before August 2025, India lacked comprehensive sports-specific legislation addressing athlete protection from harassment, abuse, or mental health crises. Consequently, incidents fell under generic laws, which proved inadequate for sport contexts. The 2013 Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act, while often applied to sports environments, has limited effectiveness because sports settings operate outside traditional workplaces, making it difficult for athletes to initiate complaints. Many cases go unreported due to the informal nature of sports environments, procedural challenges, and athletes' reluctance to report incidents to authorities who may be personally connected to perpetrators.

[Harassment and abuse remain critical issues for Indian athletes](#), manifesting in multiple forms. Physical abuse occurs through excessive training, forced participation, physical punishment, overworking, and practices leading to injury and trauma, particularly in high-performance settings like gymnastics and boxing. Sexual harassment and exploitation result from poorly defined boundaries between coaches, officials, and athletes, with high-profile cases in wrestling and gymnastics communities highlighting the power imbalances

between athletes and authorities. Psychological and emotional abuse is prevalent in high-performance environments, where athletes face immense pressure from coaches, peers, and family members, leading to manipulation, bullying, and emotional coercion. These forms of abuse often intersect, creating environments where athletes feel isolated and silenced. The absence of specific legal structures has led to alarming rates of unreported cases.

Landmark National Sports Governance Bill 2025

In August 2025, India became the 21st country to enact comprehensive sports law through the [National Sports Governance Bill](#). This landmark legislation mandates that all National Sports Body boards must include at least four women and have

athlete representation, addressing power imbalances and ensuring diverse perspectives in sport leadership. Critically, all sports must follow the forthcoming National Safe Sport Policy, which will ensure protection and safety specifically for women and minor athletes. The Bill establishes a tribunal for disputes, with all costs covered by the Indian government, removing financial barriers to justice. While the Safe Sport Policy has not yet been developed or published, its mandated implementation represents significant progress toward systematic athlete protection.

IRELAND

Ireland's Approach to Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Society and Sport

Ireland has developed a comprehensive framework addressing gender-based violence (GBV) through national strategies, sport-specific policies, and child protection legislation. While explicit integration between national GBV strategies and sport remains limited, Ireland has implemented innovative partnerships, governance structures, and safeguarding frameworks to protect athletes and promote violence prevention throughout the sport sector.

National Strategy and Legal Framework

Ireland's [Third National Domestic, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence Strategy](#) establishes the country's overarching approach to addressing GBV in society, though it does not explicitly mention sport, physical education, or physical activity. The age of sexual consent in Ireland is 17 years nationally, and Ireland maintains a mandatory [duty to report child abuse](#) at the national level, creating legal obligations for citizens to report suspected cases to authorities.

Sport-Specific Initiatives and Game Changer Project

Despite the absence of sport in the national GBV strategy, Ireland has developed targeted initiatives recognizing the sector's critical role in prevention and awareness. The "[Game Changer](#)" project represents Ireland's most direct sport-sector response to GBV. This three-year partnership between the Gaelic Athletic Association (GAA), Ruhama, and White Ribbon Ireland aims to raise awareness and drive action through sport to tackle domestic, sexual, and gender-based violence. The project leverages sport's cultural significance and community reach to challenge harmful attitudes

and behaviours, positioning athletes, coaches, and sport organizations as active agents in preventing GBV. This grassroots approach recognizes that sport environments can either perpetuate or challenge the gender norms and power dynamics that enable violence and GBV.

Ireland also has a [National Observatory on Violence against Women and Girls](#) which monitors progress on violence against women in Ireland. Their [2022 report](#) indicated the need for delivering GBV awareness education to young people in sports settings.

National Sports Policy and Governance Framework

The [National Sports Policy 2018-2027](#) and its accompanying [Sports Action Plan](#) provide Ireland's strategic direction for sport development. While the policy does not explicitly address gender-based violence or abuse in sport, it contains one mention of "violence against women" as an international focus issue and references safeguarding children in sport as a priority. This limited explicit attention to GBV in the foundational policy document suggests potential gaps in systematically addressing violence and abuse within sport environments.

However, Ireland has established robust governance structures through the [Governance Code for Sport](#), which became mandatory for adoption by all sport organizations by the end of 2021. This tiered framework establishes accountability standards and operational requirements for organizations receiving public funding, creating infrastructure through which safeguarding and welfare policies can be implemented and monitored across the sport sector.

Child Protection and Safeguarding Framework

The [2015 Children First Act](#) provides a clear framework for ensuring children and young people are safe and protected. Sports bodies receiving public funding must demonstrate full compliance with all statutory requirements, including developing mandatory [Child Safeguarding Statements](#). This legislative requirement creates baseline protections for young athletes and establishes accountability for sport organizations.

[Sport Ireland's Safeguarding Guidance for Children and Young People in Sport](#) provides comprehensive direction specifically for the sport sector. [Sport Ireland's Safeguarding Audit Framework](#) (Appendix 3) supports National Governing Bodies (NGBs) in strengthening adherence to safeguarding policies and procedures, setting expectations beyond statutory requirements of the Children First Act. Sport clubs must ensure all members are vetted through the [National Vetting Bureau](#) or Access NI, creating screening mechanisms to prevent individuals with unsuitable backgrounds from accessing vulnerable young people. Additionally, sport clubs must implement codes of conduct incorporating safeguarding practices, establishing behavioural standards and reporting mechanisms.

Athlete Welfare and Anti-Harassment Policies

Sport Ireland's [Athlete Welfare Policy](#) requires each National Governing Body to maintain a bullying and harassment policy, establishing minimum standards for addressing interpersonal violence and abuse within sport environments. This requirement ensures that organizations have formal mechanisms for preventing, reporting, and responding to harassment and bullying behaviours that can constitute or facilitate gender-based violence.

Ireland has also addressed [school-related gender-based violence](#) through dedicated guidance documents examining violence in educational settings, recognizing that young people experience violence across multiple contexts where they participate in physical activity. While sport is not directly addressed, school sports remain an environment in which children can experience GBV.

Gaps and Future Directions

Despite these frameworks, notable gaps remain, including the absence of explicit GBV language in the National Sports Policy and limited integration between the national GBV strategy and sport sector initiatives, suggesting opportunities for stronger alignment and more comprehensive athlete protection across all participation levels.

MEXICO

Mexico's Approach to Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Society and Sport

Mexico has taken significant legislative steps to address gender-based violence (GBV), particularly through groundbreaking digital violence legislation, though comprehensive sport-specific frameworks remain underdeveloped. The country's approach combines child protection definitions, criminal law reforms, and technology-focused violence prevention to create protections for women and girls across society, with implications for sport environments.

Protections for Children from Violence and Harm

Mexican law establishes clear age-based categories for protection: a minor is defined as anyone under 18 years of age, a child is under 12 years, and an adolescent is between 12 and under 18 years. These definitions provide frameworks for age-appropriate protections and inform consent laws and safeguarding requirements. Mexico has also criminalized grooming, recognizing that predatory behaviours often begin with manipulation and boundary violations before escalating to physical abuse—a pattern particularly relevant in sport settings where coaches and officials hold positions of trust and authority over young athletes. In 2023 the [Federal Criminal Code](#) was amended to accommodate the concept of grooming (encouraging, enticing, by digital means, Article 199 Septies).

Landmark "Olimpia Act" and Digital Violence Legislation

On January 22, 2020, the Government of Mexico City published the "[Olimpia Act](#)" ([Ley Olimpia](#)), also known as the "Digital Violence Act," representing groundbreaking legislation addressing technology-facilitated gender-based violence. The initiative, proposed in February 2019, aims to

criminalize anyone who, under any circumstances, transgresses against women's dignity through digital means. The reforms modified the Criminal Code for Mexico City and the Law on Women's Access to a Violence-Free Life in Mexico City, adding critical protections against digital violence. In 2021 the Federal Government of Mexico incorporated the Olimpia Act into the [Federal Law on Women's Access to a Violence-Free Life](#) (Chapter 4), applying it country wide.

The Olimpia Act defines violence against women as acts committed through Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), internet platforms, social networks, or email that threaten women's integrity, dignity, intimacy, freedom, and private life, causing psychological, physical, economic, or sexual harm in both private and public spheres. Prohibited behaviours include harassment, threats, insults, dissemination of false information, hate messages, and non-consensual sharing of intimate content including texts, photographs, videos, personal data, or other graphic or audio materials, whether authentic or altered. This is particularly relevant for female athletes whose careers and livelihoods exist largely in the public sphere, through social media.

Implications for Sport Environments

While Mexico's legislation does not explicitly reference sport, physical education, or physical activity settings, the enhanced penalties for abuse within teacher-student, employment, and subordination relationships directly apply to sport environments where coaches, officials, and administrators hold power over athletes ([Federal Criminal Code Article 209 Bis](#)). The digital violence provisions are acutely relevant given the increasing use of social media in sport contexts, where athletes face heightened vulnerability to image-based abuse, harassment, and exploitation, but may only apply specifically to

women under the law on violence against women. Technology-facilitated violence in sport can include non-consensual sharing of locker room images, cyberbullying by coaches or teammates, sexual harassment through digital communications, and online harassment campaigns targeting all athletes, including female athletes. This leaves male athletes potentially vulnerable to digital harm in sport, and beyond.

Mexico's National Commission for Physical Culture and Sport (CONADE) is the main governmental body responsible for regulating sports in Mexico, and they published a [Code of Conduct for Sport](#) in 2023 outlining ethical requirements for those who work in sport, or who "although not public officials, collaborate in achieving the objectives and goals of the public policies on physical culture and sport established by CONADE". This implies that these ethics, including zero tolerance for physical, sexual, emotional, or any form of violence (Section 7.2), are mandated for all those who fall under the umbrella of sport (participants, coaches, volunteers, etc). The [2025-2030 National Program for Physical Culture and Sports](#) indicates safe sport as a priority area for the next five years.

Future Directions

Mexico's progressive digital violence legislation establishes important legal protections applicable to sport contexts. However, developing consistent and comprehensive sport-specific safeguarding frameworks, reporting mechanisms, and athlete welfare policies applicable throughout the Nation would strengthen protections for athletes experiencing gender-based violence in training, competition, and digital spaces associated with sport participation.

MOROCCO

Morocco's Approach to Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Society and Sport

Morocco has made significant progress through [Law 103-13 on the Elimination of Violence Against Women](#), which criminalizes various forms of violence against women including sexual harassment, economic abuse, and psychological violence. This legislation provides crucial protections that extend across all sectors, including sport, establishing a legal foundation for safeguarding women and girls.

Stadium Violence and Hooliganism

[Hooliganism and fan violence at stadiums](#) remain persistent challenges in Morocco. These incidents compromise the safety of sporting events and discourage participation from families and communities, [especially women](#). This violence reflects broader societal issues and undermines sport's potential to promote positive values and bring people together. In effort to combat such violence, the Moroccan Government implemented [law 09-09 "Violence committed during or in connection with sporting competitions or events"](#) to [complete](#) the Penal Code in 2011.

Child Protection in Sporting Contexts

[Law 30-09 relating to physical education and sports](#) establishes mandatory screening requirements for individuals working with children in sport in Morocco. This legislation requires background checks and vetting procedures to ensure that those in positions of authority over young athletes are suitable for such roles and have no history of violence. The law represents an important safeguarding measure, recognizing that children in sport are vulnerable to abuse from coaches, trainers, and other personnel.

A [2025 workshop organised by ECPAT International](#) focused on building strategies to protect children during major sporting events. Participants emphasized the need to routinely integrate child protection measures into sports programs, with particular attention to gender-sensitive and survivor-centred approaches. This represents important recognition that children require specific protections in sporting environments, and that responses to abuse must be trauma-informed and appropriate for young survivors.

Women and girls face particular vulnerabilities within sporting environments. Power imbalances between coaches and athletes, limited oversight, and traditional gender norms can create conditions where abuse occurs. Workshop discussions indicated that stakeholders are beginning to address these issues more directly, recognizing that effective safeguarding must account for the gendered nature of violence in sport.

Sport Policy in Morocco

Morocco's sports policy framework outlines the country's strategic approach to developing and governing sport at all levels. [La Politique Sportive au Maroc](#) establishes guidelines for sports administration, athlete development, facility management, and the promotion of physical activity across society. The policy addresses both elite performance and grassroots participation, aiming to make sport accessible while building competitive success. The policy identifies the growing field of esports as an important focus for Morocco, as well as ensuring that women have opportunities to gain leadership roles in sport, and that actions need to be developed to prevent and address violence in sport but does not address gender-based violence specifically.

Implementation Gaps, Moving Forward

Despite legislative progress and increasing awareness, significant gaps remain in translating policy into practice. Implementing Law 103-13 within sporting contexts requires dedicated resources, comprehensive training for coaches and administrators, and accessible reporting mechanisms that survivors can use safely. Addressing stadium violence demands integrated approaches combining improved security with educational initiatives that promote respect and fair play.

Morocco must build on its legal framework and emerging awareness by developing sport-specific safeguarding policies. This includes establishing clear codes of conduct, mandatory background checks for those working with children, and safe reporting channels. Tackling both spectator violence and interpersonal abuse requires sustained commitment, adequate funding, and collaboration between government ministries, sporting organizations, and civil society. Only through such comprehensive efforts can Morocco create safe sporting environments where all participants, particularly women and children, can engage without fear of violence or exploitation.

NIGERIA

Nigeria: Gender-Based Violence and Safe Sport Overview

Sports Governance Structure

Nigeria's sports sector operates through a tripartite governance structure involving the [National Sport Commission](#) (formerly a part of the (Ministry of Youth and Sports Development) responsible for policy-setting, national sports federations (managing sport-specific governance, such as the Nigeria Football Federation), and the [Nigerian Olympic Committee](#) (overseeing Olympic sports). In 2024, the National Sports Commission was designated as the government agency responsible for sport administration, removing it from the office of the Ministry of Youth and Sports Development.

National Sports Policy Framework

The [2020 National Sports Industry Policy \(NSIP\)](#) represents Nigeria's primary strategic framework for sports development. The policy aims to leverage Nigeria's remarkable sporting talent, passion, interest, and excellence to advance diplomatic relations and, more importantly, generate employment, create jobs, increase government revenue, and bolster the economy. It identifies four key trigger factors—Infrastructure, Incentives, Investment, and Policy—as essential to achieving these ambitious goals.

The NSIP outlines eleven objectives and ten Policy Thrust Areas covering various aspects of sports development, including National Sports Federations and Athletes' Development, Sports and Education, Sports and Health, Sports Capacity Development and Training, Sports for Inclusivity and Social Development in the Community, Sports Facilities and Infrastructure, Sports for Economic Development, Sports Legislative Environment and International Relations, Funding and Investment in Sports, and

Sports and the Digital Economy. Section 5.5.2 indicates that a key challenge to achieving the goals of the policy, equality, and equity in sports is that women and girls risk sexual harassment and abuse, and a lack of safe spaces as barriers to participation in sport. Despite this acknowledgement, Nigeria lacks concrete policies or action plans on addressing these issues at the national level.

National Legislation and Gender Policy

Nigeria has enacted several relevant legislative frameworks that could apply to the sports context. [The Violence Against Persons \(Prohibition\) Act \(VAPP Act\) of 2015](#) provides a national legislative framework addressing domestic violence and other forms of violence against persons, including physical, sexual, psychological, and economic abuse. Additionally, Nigeria has a [National Gender Policy](#) designed to promote gender equality and address gender-based discrimination across various sectors. This policy does not mention sport as an area of focus.

Regarding child protection, Nigerian law establishes mandatory reporting requirements for child abuse among certain professions through the [Child Rights Act 2003](#). These duty-to-report obligations apply to professionals who work with children, including teachers, healthcare workers, and social workers. However, the specific application of these frameworks to sports professionals—such as coaches, trainers, sports medicine practitioners, and administrators—remains unclear, and there is no evident integration of these policies into sports-specific regulations or safeguarding mechanisms. There are also no known mandates on background checks or screening for those who work in sport.

Recent Safe Sport Developments

A promising development emerged in January 2025 when the Nigerian Olympic Committee established a new [Safeguard Commission](#) dedicated to promoting safe sport in Nigeria. The Commission's goals include preventing harassment, abuse, and discrimination in sports; providing support and resources to athletes and stakeholders affected by misconduct; fostering a culture of reporting and investigating allegations; and collaborating with sport federations to develop and implement effective safeguarding policies. There is no indication that this is mandatory, and as a non-governmental organisation, this is not a federal level policy or program applicable to all sports in Nigeria.

In May 2025, reports indicated that the Nigerian Olympic Committee had released a [safeguarding handbook and launched a SAFE SPACE initiative](#) at the Gateway Games to enhance athlete welfare. However, this handbook remains unavailable on public-facing pages online, and its contents cannot be independently verified, raising questions about accessibility and transparency in safeguarding implementation.

Assessment and Gaps

The current situation in Nigeria reveals a critical disconnect. While the country possesses ambitious sports development policies focused on economic growth and international competitiveness, and has national legislation and policy addressing domestic violence, gender equality, and child protection, safeguarding mechanisms and GBV prevention frameworks remain largely absent from national sports policy documents and webpages. There is no clear evidence that mandatory reporting requirements for child abuse extend explicitly to sports professionals, nor is there integration of the VAPP Act or National Gender Policy into sports governance structures.

The recent establishment of the Nigerian Olympic Committee Safeguard Commission represents an important first step toward addressing these gaps. However, the lack of publicly accessible safeguarding resources, the absence of concrete GBV actions in the National Sport Industry Policy, and unclear linkages between national legislation and sports-specific implementation suggest that substantial work remains. Nigeria needs to develop a national, comprehensive, transparent, and enforceable safe sport policy and framework that explicitly protects athletes—particularly women and children—from harassment, abuse, and discrimination within the sporting context, while clearly defining the responsibilities and reporting obligations of sports professionals.

RWANDA

Rwanda: Gender-Based Violence and Safe Sport Overview

Sports Governance Structure

Rwanda's sports sector is governed by [Law No. 32 of 2017, the Law Governing Organisation of Sport, Games and Leisure](#). This legislation codifies anti-doping regulations and establishes the structure and governance of sport at various levels throughout the country. The law provides the foundational framework for sports administration in Rwanda, though it contains no mention of safe sport or gender-based violence (GBV) in sport.

National Sports Policy Framework

The [2024-2029 Sports and Culture Sector Strategic Plan](#) outlines Rwanda's vision to build a vibrant and professional sports industry. The plan identifies two primary outcomes: increased revenues generated from sports, and increased participation in sports activities to boost Rwandans' health, wellness, and economy.

Key strategies include constructing world-class sports infrastructures, hosting international events, establishing national talent development programs, strengthening governance and management capacity of sports organizations, and attracting private sector investment. The plan emphasizes organizing sports for all, with special attention to women, the elderly, and people with disabilities, and proposes establishing a National Sports Authority (NSA-RWANDA) with an associated sports development fund.

Despite these comprehensive objectives and specific attention to vulnerable populations including women, the strategic plan contains no mention of GBV prevention or safe sport initiatives,

representing a significant gap in Rwanda's sports policy framework.

National Legislation and Gender Policy

Rwanda has enacted several relevant legislative frameworks addressing gender-based violence. In 2008, Rwanda adopted [Law No. 59/2008 on Prevention and Punishment of Gender-Based Violence](#), providing a national legislative framework specifically addressing GBV. Additionally, [Prime Minister's Order N°001/03 of 11/01/2012](#) establishes modalities for government institutions to prevent and respond to GBV by outlining their responsibilities, including implementing prevention programs, ensuring swift intervention for victims, and setting up "one-stop centres" at health facilities for emergency care and legal assistance. The order also details responsibilities for reinforcing anti-GBV committees, providing poverty reduction programs for vulnerable groups, and coordinating information sharing on prevention activities.

The most current version of the [Rwanda National Action Plan](#) includes contributions to UNSC Resolution 1325, which focuses on GBV. Rwanda's criminal code contains important protections in Article 133, indicating that sexual relations between individuals aged 14 and 18 years is not criminal unless it involves force, threats, or exploitation based on vulnerability.

Rwanda's [Revised National Gender Policy \(2021\)](#) promotes gender equality across all sectors by strengthening legal frameworks, institutional accountability, and inclusive development. It emphasizes eliminating gender-based violence, empowering women and girls, and integrating gender perspectives into education, health, governance, and economic planning. The policy aligns with international commitments like the SDGs and AU Gender Policy and supports child protection

through gender-responsive services and laws, however there is no mention of sport or sporting environments as focal areas for addressing GBV.

Child Protection and Mandatory Reporting

Regarding mandatory reporting obligations, there is no evidence that a duty to report exists for the general population in Rwanda. However, certain professions are required by policy and practice to report suspected cases. Despite Rwanda having [Law N°71/2018 of 31/08/2018 Relating to the Protection of the Child](#), and Article 29 stating that "involving a child in sport activities harmful to his/her health" is considered criminal activity, there is no indication that a duty to report abuse against a child in sport exists, nor are there screening requirements for those who work with children in sport.

Safe Sport Developments

Based on available information, there are no documented safe sport initiatives or developments in Rwanda's sports sector. The [Rwanda Sports Strategic Plan 2023-2028](#) contains no mention of safe sport or gender-based violence prevention. There is no unified or central Rwandan policy or strategic action plan on safe sport or safeguarding in sport.

Assessment and Gaps

Rwanda presents a significant disconnect between national GBV legislation and sports policy. While the country has robust frameworks addressing gender-based violence nationally (Law No. 59/2008, Prime Minister's Order N°001/03) and child protection (Law N°71/2018), these have not been integrated into sports governance. The absence of safe sport provisions in both the foundational sports law and current strategic plan represents a critical gap. There is no indication of mandatory screening for those working in sport with minors, leaving individual organizations without unified national guidance. Rwanda urgently needs to develop comprehensive safe sport policies that bridge existing GBV and child protection legislation with sports-specific safeguarding standards, reporting mechanisms, and accountability structures.

SWEDEN

Sweden: Gender-Based Violence and Safe Sport Overview

National Legislation and Gender Policy

Sweden has extensive policies and action plans on GBV/VAWG (Violence Against Women and Girls), including the [Free and safe without violence and oppression](#) action programme for the period of 2024-2026. However, there is no specific mention of sport within these broader national GBV prevention frameworks, indicating a potential gap in integrating national violence prevention strategies with sports-specific contexts.

Sweden has enacted [robust legislations](#) to combat violence against women, including expanding the principle of consent in sexual offences within the [Swedish Criminal Code](#). This legislative framework makes forced marriage and female genital mutilation crimes, demonstrating Sweden's comprehensive approach to gender-based violence prevention.

Regarding child protection, Sweden, as a signatory to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, imposes a moral [duty to report on all adults](#). This means that all adults who know about or suspect that a child is being abused or treated with violence must report it to relevant authorities. However, only certain professions and types of organizations, such as schools and health centres, are obligated by law to report suspected abuse or harm of children. This is legislated through the [Social Services Act, Chapter 14](#).

Legal Age of Child and Age of Consent in Sweden

In Sweden, [a child is defined as anyone under 18 years of age](#), consistent with the Convention on the Rights of the Child. The age of consent for sexual relations is 15 years old. However, if a person

over 18 years is in a position of trust or authority over a 15–17-year-old, the age of consent is raised to 18. As long as [proper consent is acquired and no position of trust exists](#), sexual relations between a person over 18 and someone aged 15-17 are not illegal under Swedish law.

Sports Governance, Policy and Safe Sport

The [Ministry of Health and Social Affairs](#) is the overarching branch of government responsible for sport policy within Sweden. Sweden's sports sector operates under the governance of the [Swedish Sports Confederation](#) (Riksidrottsförbundet), which has created a document on [creating safe and inclusive sports environments](#), with guidelines for how sport organizations should approach safe sport and policies. Additionally, Sweden has established a [Sports Ombudsman](#) program specifically designed for reporting safe sport issues, providing an independent mechanism for addressing concerns related to harassment, abuse, and discrimination in sports.

These initiatives reflect Sweden's commitment to creating safe and inclusive sporting environments, though the effectiveness of these programs depends on their implementation across all levels of sport and continued monitoring and evaluation. Since 2018 sport in Sweden has been led by [Strategy 2025](#) as the guiding policy for the sport sector, with the new strategy/policy [Swedish Sport 2035](#) coming into effect in 2026. While this new strategy mentions safe and inclusive spaces and gender equality as priorities, it does not directly address gender-based violence in sport. The strategy represents Sweden's vision for creating an equitable and accessible sports environment, though the specific mechanisms for preventing and responding to GBV and violence within sport require further elaboration through complementary policies and action plans.

Assessment and Gaps

Sweden presents a relatively advanced framework for addressing GBV and safe sport compared to many countries. The country has strong national legislation on violence against women, mandatory reporting requirements for suspected child abuse (with enhanced obligations for certain professions), and sports-specific safeguarding initiatives including the Sports Ombudsman program.

However, a critical gap remains: while Sweden has extensive national policies on GBV/VAWG and a national sports strategy that mentions safe spaces, there is no direct integration between these frameworks. The national action programmes addressing violence against women do not specifically mention sport, and conversely, the sports strategy does not directly address gender-based violence prevention, nor are the safeguarding initiatives mandatory.

To strengthen its approach, Sweden should explicitly integrate GBV prevention into sports policy, ensure that sports professionals understand their reporting obligations under the Social Services Act, and continue developing the Sports Ombudsman program as a model for athlete protection. The existing foundation is strong, but bridging the gap between national GBV policy and sports-specific implementation would create a more comprehensive and effective safeguarding system that protects all participants of sport.

SWITZERLAND

Switzerland: Gender-Based Violence and Safe Sport Overview

National Legislation and Gender Policy

Switzerland has made [amendments to criminal legislation](#) to better account for different forms of domestic violence, including provisions for those both in and not in relationships. These amendments include the addition of stalking to the criminal code and provisions addressing female genital mutilation, demonstrating Switzerland's commitment to comprehensive legal protections against gender-based violence.

Switzerland's [National Action Plan for the Istanbul Convention](#) addresses gender-based violence prevention across multiple sectors. Objective 31 specifically focuses on "Raising awareness among sports instructors/leaders in the training and further education programs of the Federal Office of Sport (FOSPO)," representing a direct effort to integrate GBV prevention into the sports context.

Regarding child protection, there is no general duty to report suspected child abuse for the general population, however [all professionals who regularly work with children](#) are legally obligated to report suspected or known child abuse, and some Cantons may have more stringent requirements than others, creating variability in child protection enforcement across the country.

Sports Governance Structure

Sport organisations in Switzerland are largely self-governed, with the [Federal Office for Sport \(BASPO\)](#) serving as the centralized service, education, and training centre within the Swiss Government. There is no centralised source of national sport policy; instead, the Federal government acts

as a funder and promoter, while Cantons and municipalities implement sport at the local level.

[Swiss Olympic](#) acts as an umbrella organisation/governing body for individual Swiss Sports Federations, which in turn are governing bodies for specific sports. In July 2024, the Disciplinary Chamber of Swiss Sports was replaced with the [Swiss Sports Tribunal](#), an independent judicial appellate body responsible for resolving disputes and imposing sanctions, particularly regarding doping and ethical violations (including safe sport violations).

Safe Sport Policy and Ethical Standards

Switzerland has implemented far-reaching reforms in response to well-publicised cases of athlete abuse, [particularly in gymnastics](#). The Swiss government mandated that sports associations must comply with a [number of new reforms to sport governance](#) and ethical statutes approved by the Swiss Parliament in 2021 to continue receiving state funding. An independent reporting office with investigatory powers and a disciplinary body with sanctioning powers were introduced to ensure accountability.

Based on their umbrella governance role in sport through Article 18 Para. 2 of the [Federal Act on the Promotion of Sport and Exercise \(SpoFöG\)](#) and Article 72c ff. of the [Regulation of promotion of sport and exercise \(SpoFöV\)](#), Swiss Olympic developed the [Statutes on Ethics in Swiss Sport](#), binding industry standards in collaboration with FOSPO, published in 2024, in effect from 1 January 2025. These statutes establish requirements for federal funding eligibility, focusing on good governance practices and adhering to the [Charter of Ethics](#). Sports organizations must incorporate recognition of the ethics charter, ethics and doping statutes, and recognition of [Swiss Sport Integrity](#) and the

[Swiss Sports Tribunal](#) bodies into their statutes. The establishment of Swiss Sport Integrity as an independent body represents Switzerland's commitment to robust safeguarding mechanisms.

Additionally, from 1 Jan 2025 Switzerland requires a [mandatory women's quota of 40%](#) on Olympic and national sport boards, promoting gender equity in sports leadership.

Background Checks and Screening in Swiss Sport

While [background checks](#) are standard practice in some employment sectors in Switzerland, such as finance, banking, and health, there are no statutory regulations requiring background checks in other sectors, including sports. The sports sector remains self-governed in this regard. Although it is considered best practice to conduct background checks on those who work with vulnerable persons, there are no legal requirements for sport organizations or for those working with children. Notably, the Ethics in Sport Charter also does not include any background check requirements.

However, one exception exists within the [Federal Act on the Promotion of Sport and Exercise](#). Article 10 indicates that in circumstances where there is reason to believe or suspect that a person has committed a criminal offense that is incompatible with their position as a "Youth and Sport" leader, the Federal Office of Sport (FOSPO) shall conduct checks on the person concerned. This provision applies specifically to Youth and Sport leaders and is reactive rather than preventive, requiring suspicion or belief of criminal activity before checks are conducted, rather than requiring proactive screening of all individuals working with children in sport. It is also unclear as to whether this requirement stands when the individual in question would be working with adult sport participants.

Assessment and Gaps

Switzerland has made significant progress through its mandatory ethical code, independent reporting and disciplinary mechanisms, and gender equity requirements. The integration of GBV awareness into Federal Office of Sport training programs represents systematic abuse prevention efforts.

The decentralized nature of child protection reporting requirements across Cantons creates inconsistency in safeguarding implementation. While Switzerland's approach to sport emphasizes self-governance with federal oversight through funding compliance, ensuring consistent implementation of safeguarding standards across all Cantons and sports organizations remains an ongoing challenge.

ZAMBIA

Zambia: Gender-Based Violence and Safe Sport Overview

National Legislation and Gender Policy

Zambia has enacted comprehensive legislation addressing gender-based violence (GBV) and gender equality. The [Anti Gender-Based Violence Act 2010](#) defines various forms and acts which may constitute gender-based violence and establishes clear procedures for how GBV is to be dealt with from the point of complaint through protection orders and criminal offenses. Importantly, the Act lays out the details for the Gender-Based Violence Committee responsible for monitoring and making recommendations on actions against GBV, and for the development of a GBV Fund to support and rehabilitate victims of GBV in Zambia. However, there is no mention of sport or physical activity within this legislation, representing a gap in applying GBV prevention frameworks to the sports context.

The [Gender Equity and Equality Act 2015](#) lays out all forms of discrimination against women as being illegal. Part V, Article 28.2(c) specifically lays out the requirement of the government to ensure the participation of women, on an equal basis with men, in recreational activities, sports, and all aspects of cultural life. This provision recognizes the importance of gender equity in sport and recreation, though it focuses on access and participation rather than safety and protection from violence.

In 2016 the government [amended the Constitution of Zambia](#), establishing principles of equality and non-discrimination, providing for a Gender Equality Commission, and underpinning the anti-GBV legislation including the Anti-Gender Based Violence Act (2011) and Gender Equity and Equality Act (2015). It supports GBV Fast Track Courts while permitting customary law that may conflict with constitutional equality principles.

Zambia's National Gender Policy 2023 on Gender-Based Violence

The [2023 National Gender Policy](#) recognizes Gender-Based Violence (GBV) as a public health issue and a violation of human rights. While GBV affects both sexes, most victims are females and perpetrators are predominantly males, due to unequal power relations between men and women, boys and girls.

One of the Policy's main objectives is to eliminate all forms of Gender-Based Violence, with measures including strengthening legislation and enforcement of GBV laws, improving knowledge and practices on GBV prevention and response, promoting female and male partnership in fighting GBV, and increasing access to essential services for victims. Zambia Police Service reported 33,536 GBV cases in 2022 compared to 20,540 in 2021, showing a 63.3% increase, with 76.5% of victims being female.

However, the National Gender Policy 2023 only mentions sport when referring to the various ministries and organizations of Zambia and their respective responsibilities. There is no comprehensive discussion of gender-based violence prevention in sport, safeguarding mechanisms, or specific strategies for addressing gender inequality and safety concerns within sporting contexts. The policy focuses primarily on participation and access rather than protection and safety for athletes.

Child Protection and Mandatory Reporting

Based on available information, there is no indication of specific child protection laws or mandatory abuse reporting requirements in Zambia related to sports or those working with children in sporting contexts. This represents a significant gap in safeguarding frameworks for young athletes. The [Teaching Profession Act, 2013](#) indicates that teachers may be required to be screened for criminal history, but it is unclear if this is mandatory, and would only affect sport run by teachers in school.

Sports Governance and Policy

The [National Sports Policy](#) and its [Implementation Plan](#), which was renewed in 2023, acknowledges that sport can be a vehicle for promoting gender equity and non-discrimination. The policy specifically recognizes the role of sport in changing gender dynamics and indicates that Sport Ministry will work with other Ministries to develop and agree on laws and policies that will support the growth and development of sport for all, including for women, girls, persons with disabilities, elderly, and youth, among others. The policy includes provisions for social justice, human trafficking, and corruption.

The National Sport Policy also indicates that the [National Olympic Committee of Zambia](#) (NOCZ) has developed and implemented a safeguarding policy, which has been adopted by the National Sports Council (a division of the [Department of Sport Development](#)). However, there is currently no such document to be found on the website of NOCZ or the National Sports Council.

Despite these progressive acknowledgments on safe sport, there are currently no mandates on how to go about screening those who work with children or adults in sports. The absence of mandatory background checks or screening

requirements for sports professionals represents a critical vulnerability in athlete protection, regardless of the Policy's good intentions.

Sport-Based GBV Prevention Initiatives

A 2022 [World Bank report on gender-based violence in Zambia](#) highlighted innovative interventions using sport to address GBV at the community level. These interventions focus on engaging men and boys to introduce them to the concept of GBV and educate them on how they are critical as allies in addressing gender-based violence. This approach recognizes the important role that male engagement plays in preventing violence against women and girls.

The same report indicated that [Sport in Action](#), a civil society organization, is working to tackle cultural and social norms as a way of preventing GBV. This demonstrates that while formal policy frameworks may be lacking, grassroots organizations are utilizing sport as a tool for social change and violence prevention.

Assessment and Gaps

Zambia presents a mixed picture regarding GBV and safe sport. The country has strong national legislation through the Anti-Gender-Based Violence Act and the Gender Equity and Equality Act 2015, which provides a foundation for addressing violence and discrimination. The National Sports Policy acknowledges the role of sport in promoting gender equity.

Critical gaps remain. There is no integration of GBV prevention into sports-specific legislation or policies, no mandatory reporting requirements for suspected abuse in sports, and no background screening requirements for those working with children in sport. While civil society organizations are conducting innovative sport-based GBV prevention programs, these efforts are not supported by comprehensive policy frameworks or safeguarding standards at the national level. Zambia needs to develop sport-specific safeguarding policies that integrate existing GBV legislation with clear standards, reporting mechanisms, and screening requirements to protect athletes, particularly women and children, from harassment, abuse, and discrimination in sport.

Annex: Additional Resources

[Sport and GBV Policies and Legislation: Dataset](#)

[CEDAW Explainer & Timeline](#)

[Directory of Knowledge Institutions and Initiatives working on GBV and Sport](#)

[Good Practice in Building a Knowledge and Learning Community: The International Safeguards for Children in Sport](#)

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